

**LAND USE CHANGE AT THE COASTAL AREA OF GANDIOL, SENEGAL,
CAUSED BY THE BREACH IN 2003 OF LA LANGUE DE BARBARIE**

BY

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ABSTRACT

Coastal erosion will become a major impact of climate change. Urbanization in the coastlines and consequent intense use of the coast resources such as freshwater or land will exacerbate the impacts of sea level rise, storms, and flooding. The purpose of this study is to assess land cover change in Gandiol, south of the city of Saint Louis in Senegal due to the resulting erosion and salinization of the land from a man-made breach at the protective sand spit called La Langue de Barbarie. Satellite imagery from diverse years (2003, 2006, 2014 and 2020) is studied by the creation of (1) vegetation quality maps by computing Soil Adjusted Vegetation Indices (SAVIs), (2) SAVIs difference rasters to compare changes, (3) land cover classification by means of Maximum Likelihood Classification (MLC), (4) land cover change map from combination of MLCs and finally the (5) qualitative and quantitative characterization of study results. These results show changes in the land that represent an abandonment of agricultural and cattle grazing lands due to salinization. It also shows the erosion of La Langue de Barbarie that is situated opposite to the Gandiol area, a few kilometers south of Saint Louis. And finally, it shows changes in vegetation health and an increase of certain types (Sahelian grass savannah). The research contributes to better understand coastal erosion and seawater intrusion and its implications on land cover change. This is useful not only for the study site but globally as 10% of the population live next to the sea.

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One day after reading and reading literature to find a Capstone topic, I remembered a friend, Sonia Håkansson, telling me about Gandiol. She once visited Hahatay, an organization founded by Mamadou Dia after reaching the Canary Islands in a boat, risking his life like many others, trying to find a better future. After some years in Spain, he decided to come back and founded the NGO. It became a space for community development, for a better future in Gandiol, his home. I already had a connection with Senegal and a trip planned to visit dear friends this past January, so I took the opportunity and also visited Hahatay. They showed me around and they showed me a life I want to be part of. Finally, I managed to find a topic that was not only interesting but dear to my heart: the salinization at Gandiol due to the breach.

During COV-ID 19, the uncertainty and stress filled my days, having to leave The Hague from one day to the other, without saying goodbye and without knowing when I will be able to come back. I reached my home in the Canary Islands to be in quarantine and lockdown for three months. During this time, the faces, and the memory of the people of Gandiol followed me and kept me going when it seemed that nothing mattered anymore. My gratitude is firstly to them, to Hahatay, for welcoming me like another member of the family. Specially to Masseur Btiye and Papa Ndara Diop for their immense smiles and will to accompany me everywhere and show me their home, to Souleymane, the lighthouse guardian, for telling me about the past, and to Amadou Mbaye for helping me understand the differences and similarities between us and our realities.

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And remember:

FII LÉPP MËN N'A NEKK

Everything is possible

1. Introduction

Amid climate change research for future adaptation or mitigation strategies, coastal erosion will pose multiple challenges to society (Walter 2018, Elkin & Keenan 2018,). Coastal zones are highly vulnerable to impacts from climate change (Dia 2000, UN 2017, Goebel et al. 2017). Multiple developed and developing countries whose main cities and population live next to the sea or are directly dependent on it will suffer from the impacts of a changing climate (Biswas et al. 2015, Walter 2018, Jana 2013, Mbuh et al. 2012, McLaughlin et al. 2002, Ndour et al. 2018, Sanò et al. 2011, Sanyang 2001, Walter 2018). These climate change impacts can also be exacerbated by other human-induced factors such as breaches in protective land to ease flooding brought by rivers or the construction of dams and levees upstream that disturb the estuarine coastal environments (Dia 2000, Walter 2018, Deroin et al. 2012). Furthermore, each case might show a different response . This is due to shorelines being highly dynamic, and at constant change spatially and temporally in response to coastal-driven, climate-driven, and human-driven processes that affect them (Mbuh et al. 2012, Goebel et al. 2017).

One of the main problems that will arise with coastal erosion is the salinization of freshwater resources, and the land (Khalil et al.2013). The management of this resource that comprises only 30% of the Earth's freshwater becomes essential for a sustainable future not only to avoid salinization by excessive pumping of freshwater but to prevent, mitigate or adapt to

seawater intrusion by rising sea levels or other geologic processes (Hudson 2020, Dia 2000, Goebels et al. 2017, Eissa et al. 2016, Kacimov et al. 2009). The salinization would degrade the water quality and decrease agricultural yields (Hudson 2020). This area is characterized by cambisols rich in clay which with increased salinization prevents infiltrability of rainwater and overflow water from the river that feed the aquifers (Diaw et al. 2010).

Furthermore, this can lead to losing arable land which puts at risk the local communities who depend on it for their own consumption but also for their income (Hudson 2020, Seck 2014, Mietton et al. 2007). The loss of fertile soil is a high threat for future generations. Soil is a finite and non-renewable natural resource (Biwas et al. 2015). It takes between 200 to 1000 years to create just 2.5 cm of topsoil under suitable conditions (Pimentel et al. 1995). Therefore, salinization of the fertile lands and aquifers is not only worrying but irreversible over human timescales.

This capstone focuses on a man-made measure: a breach put in place to avoid flooding in the city of Saint Louis that created negative consequences for the populations living south of the city in the study site of the Gandiol area (also called Gandiolais). Coastal erosion that might have been a problem eventually due to future climatic changes become a problem in a matter of hours destroying villages, touristic potential, agricultural lands, pasture, and fishermen's economy (Mietton et al. 2007, Sy BA et al. 2013, Seck 2014, Wade et al. 2008). This has led to the abandonment of agriculture and cattle, and to migration to other parts of Senegal in search of jobs or more opportunities, but also to Mauritania, and sometimes to the Canary Islands by using the *pirogues*, fishermen's boats trying to reach for Europe (Sy et al. 2014, Fofana et al. 2017, Sy T 2006).

2. Project overview

The study site is situated in the Gandiolais, a rural area a few kilometers south of the city of Saint Louis in Senegal and it consists of the villages of Gandiol Ndiébène, Pilote Barre and Tassinère. All these villages relied on market gardening and fishery for its subsistence before the breach in 2003 (Seck 2014, Sy BA 2015). However, they have been threatened by the advancement of seawater, which is causing salinization of the river and agricultural lands, endangering the economy (Isupova et al. 2008, Champalbert et al. 2014, Mietton et al. 2007). The breach, an effort to protect the vulnerable city of Saint Louis, resulted in these villages becoming extremely vulnerable to land erosion, salinization of agricultural land and the river, loss of tourism potential, flooding, and invasive species, among others (Seck 2014, Dumas et al. 2010, Mietton et al. 2007). Therefore, this area presents socio economic and ecological risks that should be monitored. The purpose of this study is to assess the change in land cover at the study site due to the breach at the Langue de Barbarie using GIS and remote sensing data. The following objectives are required to complete this study:

1. Creation of vegetation quality maps for 2003, 2006, 2014 and 2020 using the Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI) from satellite imagery.
2. Creation of land cover maps for 2003, 2006, 2014 and 2020 using satellite imagery and image classification procedures (Maximum Likelihood Classification).
3. The creation of SAVI difference raster for the periods (1) 2003 to 2006, (2) 2006 to 2014, (3) 2014 to 2020 and (4) 2003 to 2020.
4. Creation of land cover change map.
5. Qualitative and quantitative characterization of study results.

3. Background

The Senegal River, born in the Fouta Djallon Mountains of Guinea, is 1800 km long and comprehends a river basin of 340,000 km² that travels through four countries: Mali, Mauritania, Guinea, and Senegal. It is the second longest river of West Africa and a driving force for the region (Fig.1) (Bouisse et al. 2011, Deroin et al. 2012, Merem et al. 2008). It can be found at latitudes 10'30 and 17'30 N and longitudes 7'30 and 16' 30 W (Merem et al. 2008). The city of Saint Louis is situated at its estuary (Mietton et al. 2007, Isupova et al 2008). Before 2003, the river's mouth was located several kilometers south of Saint Louis, and the city and rural areas were protected by a sand spit called Langue de Barbarie (Fig.3) (Mietton et al. 2007). Flooding occurred frequently in the rainy season (June to September) (Merem et al. 2008, Dia et al. 2004, Bouisse et al. 2011, WWAP 2003).

In 1986 a dam was built a few kilometers upstream from the city (Dumas et al. 2010, Dia et al. 2004, Deroin et al. 2012). This dam, called Diama dam, was originally put in place to avoid salinization but later became a support for irrigated agriculture and an essential infrastructure to prevent flooding in the city (Dumas et al. 2010). This dam and the Manantali dam further upstream have proven to be beneficial for the region converting a seasonal marked environment to a low-flow perennial freshwater regime providing freshwater all year around, incrementing agriculture and drinking water access (WWAP 2003). The negative effects are the displacement of populations, alterations and degradation of the previous ecosystem and the rise of water-borne diseases (WWAP 2003). Floods decreased by twofold relative to the first half of the 20th century since the construction of the Diama dam, with controversy about whether it was due to the dam or to the decrease in rainfall (Deroin et al. 2012). In response to this calm period, there was a huge urbanization increase in low-lying parts of the city (Dumas et al. 2010). In 2003, a major

flood occurred which carried $3660 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ of water. Before the dams were built the river flow during flood events was frequently more than $6500 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Champalbert et al. 2014, Deroin et al. 2012, Sakho et al. 2017). However, as urbanization had grown uncontrollably, people living in the vulnerable areas were affected by the flooding, losing material goods, their homes and, in some cases, human lives (Deroin et al. 2012, Sanyang. 2001, Diaw et al. 2007). During this 2003 flood, a 4 meters wide human-made breach was cut in the Barbarie spit to release water to the sea which rapidly grew naturally despite efforts to avoid it and is now more than 5 kilometers long (Fig.2) (Sy BA et al. 2013). The short-term impacts of the breach were the destruction of villages south of Saint Louis and the increased vulnerability to land degradation and coastal erosion of the Gandiol sector (Sy BA 2015).

Figure 1. The Senegal River Basin. Source: Musser 2010.

Figure 2. Time-space evolution of the breach at the *Langue de Barbarie* and new mouth of the Senegal river between October 2003 and April 2006. Source: Dumas. 2010.

In a world threatened by sea level rise and flooding, this case study becomes essential in order to understand how lethal the sea can be to the livelihoods depending on it or depending on the protection from it by other natural actors (Ndour et al. 2018). This study investigates the land use change from months before the breach, to a couple of years after (2006), a decade after (2014) and at the present time (2020) in the area of Gandiol comprising the villages of Pilote Barre, Gandiol Ndiébène and Tassinère. Using remote sensing and GIS techniques, the change in the land use and vegetation quality and quantity can be monitored.

Figure 3. Senegal River Basin and its new mouth due to the breach at the Languede Barbarie in 2003.

Source: Mietton et al. 2007.

4. Literature Review

4.1. Solutions to the droughts

The Senegal River Valley and other regions of West Africa experienced severe droughts during the 1970s and 1980s (Karambiri et al. 2011, Sakho et al. 2017, Dumas et al. 2010). These intense droughts brought an agricultural crisis, famines, refugees, etc. (Sakho et al. 2017). Senegal relies and continues to rely on rice imports for alimentation, making the society vulnerable not only to droughts but also to relying on foreign markets (Blanc et al. 2015, Diagne et al. 2013). To prevent this from happening again in the future and to become self-sufficient, two dams were built to support gravitational irrigated agriculture and a project called GOANA was launched to transform the Senegal river valley, from a seasonal economy of hunting and gathering to an extensive permanent irrigated agriculture economy (Dumas et al. 2010, WWAP 2003, FAO 1997). The Diama dam (1986) was built closer to the Senegal River estuary to regulate water levels and quality by blocking the intrusion of seawater (Dumas et al. 2010, Bouisse et al. 2011, Diaw et al. 2010). The Manantali dam (1987) was built upstream in Mali with a storage function and regulating function to produce electricity, control flow and support dry seasons flow, provide water for irrigation and navigation (Dumas et al. 2010, Bouisse et al. 2011, Diaw et al. 2010, Sakho et al. 2017, Bouisse et al. 2011).

Unfortunately, water became insufficient for currently developed irrigated land (Bouisse et al. 2011). The GOANA project had targets that could not be achieved, as farmers struggled and still struggle to cope with adversity (land levelling problems, poor conditions of irrigation canals, etc.) (Diagne et al. 2013). Furthermore, GOANA was only based on spatial and temporal extension of rice irrigation scheme but not on other sources of productivity growth, making the crops vulnerable to adverse events or market imperfections (Diagne et al. 2013, Dumas et al.

2010). These dams' main function became to control river flow to avoid flooding and salinization (Dumas et al. 2010).

4.2. Floods

The flow of the Senegal River follows a regime of distinct dry and rainy seasons (Bouisse et al. 2011, Deroin et al. 2012, WWAP 2003, Frederiksen et al. 1992). The river is under diverse climatic conditions, as it travels from Fouta Djalon mountains to the coast, from forests to savannahs to dry Sahel lands. In the mountains where it originates the rainfall goes up to 2000 mm, whereas in the low Senegal River precipitation is less than 300 mm (Merem et al. 2008). The annual streamflow regime (Fig.4) shows the distinct seasons and precipitation patterns. The rain season goes mainly from June-July to October, the dry cold and warm seasons go from November to May (Isupova et al. 2008, Bouisse et al. 2011, Deroin et al. 2012, WWAP 2003). Streamflow is quite low in the dry season in the months from January to June (< 250mm). As precipitation increases, streamflow increases in the months June-July with a peak in October of 2250 mm (Fig.4). The hydrograph data was retrieved from Dagana station, about 120 km upstream of the estuary.

Figure 4. Hydrograph from Dagana station, 120 km from Saint Louis upstream of the Senegal River, Senegal (1903 – 1974). Source: UNH/ GRDC.

The floods are a frequent and essential element for the floodplains of the Senegal River (Deroin et al., Diaw et al. 2007, Merem et al. 2008). The severity is assessed when it harms people, their activities, and their infrastructure (crops, houses, etc.). Several factors increase the intensity of the floods such as heavier rains and thus heavier flow, temporal obstruction of the river mouth (Fig.3) by sediments, stagnation of rainwater in the city, urbanizing in floodplains, and the absence of an appropriate drainage network, among others (Diaw et al. 2007, Karambiri et al. 2011, Mietton et al. 2007).

Close to the mouth of the Senegal river lies the city of Saint Louis on an island surrounded by the water of the river, thus vulnerable by nature (Dia et al. 2004) When river water levels exceed 1.2 meters above mean sea level, flooding occurs in Saint Louis (Dia et al. 2004). Flooding has occurred nine times since 1964, and only three times since the dams were built (Dia et al. 2004). The Manantali and Diama dam have, therefore, both proved useful to prevent flooding (Dumas et al. 2010).

4.3. The Breach

In October 2003, a human induced breach was cut in the Langue de Barbarie to further mitigate floods (Champalbert et al. 2014, Dumas et al. 2010, Dia et al. 2004). It had an initial extension of only 4 meters, a decade later it was larger than 4 kilometers, having increased with an average annual widening of 400m/year (Sakho et al. 2017). This improvised solution became worse than the original affliction (Dumas et al. 2010, Mietton et al. 2007). Villages south of Saint Louis, directly adjacent to the breach disappeared, as the breaking of the Langue de Barbarie left the land without protection from the sea, allowing massive and disastrous erosion and penetration of seawater to the estuary (Mietton et al. 2007, Deroin et al. 2012). Moreover, the maximum flow had already been observed a week before at Bakel, a gauging station (Deroin et al. 2012).

Therefore, the breach was not needed to stop of the flood. As it was already decreasing and had no direct impact in the lowering of the waters.

The flood of 2003 was not exceptional, but it was aggravated by the impediment of flow downriver by a partial blocking of the old river mouth (Fig.3) (Dumas et al. 2010, Diaw et al. 2007). Additionally, the impacts of the flood were due to Saint Louis' own self-induced vulnerability (Mietton et al. 2007, Dumas et al. 2010). With the construction of the dams, and the absence of flooding for some years, people started migrating to the city (Karambiri et al. 2011, Mietton et al. 2007). The urban growth was faster than the government could manage in terms of planning and provision of services (Sanyang, 2001). Population expanded without control to low lying parts of the town due to overconfidence during the years without floods and thus were extremely vulnerable during the flood of 2003 (Dumas et al. 2010).

The 2003 flood carried $3660 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ which was higher than the normal river flow for October that of around $2250 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Fig.4). However, before the dams were built, floods tend to occur with peak discharges greater than $6500 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Sakho et al. 2017). Therefore the high impacts that this flood had on the population was mainly due to Saint Louis' own vulnerability and the breach that was cut in the sandpit to discharge water was a last-minute solution that became irreversible and greatly impacted the estuary of the river and the Gandiolais area.

4.4. Impact on Gandiol

The Gandiolais area of various villages shows the most striking changes due to the breach (Seck 2014, Sy BA 2015, Dumas et al. 2010, Mietton et al. 2007, Isupova et al. 2008). The villages of Doun Baba Dièye and Keur Bernard completely disappeared and the ones further south still face these impacts (Seck 2014, Sy BA 2015). Among them: erosion which destroys houses, hotels and protected areas, the destabilization of coastal dunes which results in high loss of fixing

vegetation, drying up of freshwater points, salinization of soils, mangroves have decreased, salty depressions have increased...(Seck 2014, Sy BA 2015). Gandiol has become increasingly vulnerable to these impacts (Ginkel et al. 2013). Despite this, there is a gap in the literature about the extent of these impacts in this specific area (Deroin et al. 2012, Merem et al. 2008).

Finally, whatever solutions might be put in place, there is a need to first understand the economic, environmental, and social costs of these effects and their extent (Cañedo et al.2013). For that reason, this study measures and assesses the impact of the breach at the study site as a basis for further research and further management of the area.

4.5 International Scope

Coastal erosion and sea level rise will pose a problem to multiple communities around the globe (Walter 2018, Kacimov et al. 2009, Goebels et al. 201, Eissa et al. 2016, Khalil et al. 2013, Mensah et al. 2013, Musa et al. 2016). By 2017, more than 600 million people lived in coastal areas less than 10 meters above sea level (UN 2017). This is 10% of the world's population. Most cases show saltwater intrusion, coastal erosion and thus loss of property and livelihoods, economic stagnation, water scarcity, etc. The Gandiol case, was not created by sea level rise or coastal erosion on its own. It was a human measure that created the disaster, which is not common but there are some examples globally (Deroin et al. 2012). The breach has made the land vulnerable to coastal erosion. and sea level rise will exacerbate the problem. Therefore, this capstone helps to understand possible outcomes from salinization and coastal erosion that will largely affect the world's population living next to the sea.

5. Study area

This study is situated at Gandiol, including the villages of Pilote Barre, Tassinère and Ndiébène Gandiol (Fig.5). It comprises a 36.65 km² rural area a few kilometers south of the city of Saint Louis in Senegal. These three villages are situated close together between the lake of Ndiébène to the river and the sea. Before the breach was cut, the river and land were protected by the sand spit. After 2013, the land was exposed directly to the sea and a new sand spit started to form naturally from the dynamics of the river and the sea (Fig.5.d).

There are four main economic sectors in the study area: agriculture, livestock, fishery, and tourism. In all these sectors, there has been a decrease in productivity that directly affects people's earnings. The salinization of the land has led to abandonment of the agricultural fields and the lack of freshwater has led to the abandonment of traditional livestock practices in the absence of freshwater wells. Erosion has destroyed the coastline where tourism mostly occurred. The river has become salinized, with deeper waters and vulnerable to the force and currents of the sea and a decrease in fish stocks.

Market gardening agriculture in the Gandiolais area plays an important role, not only in their economy, being the first sector but in the culture, rhythm, identity, and place attachment of Gandiol (Sy BA 2015). For example, in Ndiébène Gandiol, market gardening covers over 700 ha and is part of 1235 households. The performance of the plants has also greatly decreased from 6,7 tonnes of product per ha (in this case tomatoes) to 1,2 tonnes per ha (Sy BA 2015). Overall, production has dropped more than 500% in less than two decades (Sy BA 2015). Farmers have tried to move the agriculture to the east. However, lands further inland have also become threatened by the breach. Market gardening is mostly manual and relies on groundwater which is also sensitive to augmentation of salinity due to the intrusion of seawater to the river. A

visualization of this problem is that the land is being sold not based on area but on how many useful wells it has (Sy BA 2015).

Therefore, along with erosion, the biggest problem of the area is to lose the fertility of the land when salinized and to lose freshwater for agriculture, livestock, and everyday living (Lange et al. 2012, Sy BA 2015). Along with fishery and tourism, these sectors have been moved either to the East (for agriculture and livestock), have been abandoned (agriculture and livestock), moved to the South (tourism) or to the north in Mauritania (fishery) (Sy BA 2015). Some will risk their lives to cross the Atlantic Ocean towards the Canary Islands or cross the desert to reach Morocco and later Spain (Sy T 2006). This contrasts with times before the breach where migrants would come to work at Gandiol. Nowadays the population of Gandiol must rely strongly on their family members migrating and on nearby territories such as Saint Louis or Podor.

(a) 2003, Landsat 7

(b) 2006, Landsat 5

(c) 2014, Landsat 8

(d) 2020, Landsat 8

Study area

Remote Sensing Images

- Red
- Green
- Blue

N
↑

0 0,5 1 2 Km

Figure 5. Study area of Gandiol, in (a) 2003, from Landsat 7, (b) 2006, Landsat 5 TM, (c) 2014, Landsat 8, and (d) 2020, Landsat 8. Data from US Geological Survey (USGS).

5.1 Vegetation of study area

Vegetation is a key element of this study. There are two main vegetation types named in this study as “low vegetation” and “vegetation” (table 3). The “low vegetation” refers to the main type of vegetation of the land that is influenced by soil and utmost by the annual precipitation which is less than 300 mm (Olsen et al. 2015, Frederiksen et al. 1992). This is the Sahelian short grass savannah and is made of grass and occasional trees and shrubs such as *Calotropis procera* and *Balanites aegyptiaca*. The soil is mainly arenosols and cambisols (Frederiksen et al. 1992, Olsen et al. 2015, CILS 2016). These grasslands have low woody density, vegetation is scattered. The vegetation is deciduous and partly evergreen. Another common vegetation types of the grassland are: *Boscia Senegalensis*, *Acacia tortilis*, *Combretum glutinosum*, *Sclerocarya birrea*, *Feretia apodanthera*, *Grewia bicolor*, *Acacia Senegal*, *Acacia seyal*, *Maerua crassifolia* and *Maytenus senegalensis* (Frederiksen et al. 1992, Seck 2014).

Figure 6. Sahelian short grass savannah defined as “low vegetation”. Source: USGS.

The “vegetation” includes mangroves influenced by salt concentration, vegetation growing densely in the fixated dunes of La Langue de Barbarie (mainly in 2003), and vegetation

that occurs at the floodplains next to the river or lakes and mainly grows in the humid summer, influenced by precipitation and river discharge. Although some of the later vegetation remains constant, not all land adjacent to the river presents this type of vegetation as the images were retrieved from the dry season and thus vegetation cover mainly disappears. Only those in a constant freshwater location remains. These areas are also used for irrigated agriculture (Bouisse et al. 2011, WWAP 2003, Frederiksen et al. 1992, Isupova et al. 2008). In the study area it occurs mainly in the North-East creating a river forest gallery in a stream of the Senegal River (Fig.5) (Wade et al. 2001). There are some patches next to lakes and around the sandpit (mainly for the 2003 year). It is expected that this type of vegetation decreases as seawater intrusion occurs. From 1979 to 2007 the mangroves have decreased to 60% mainly due to changes in hydrology and in the water table (Seck 2014). The vegetation is more densely spaced. Mangroves are evergreen, some common species for are: *Laguncularia racemose*, *Avicennia africana*, *Rhizophora mangle*. The vegetation densely growing in the dunes is *Prosopis juliflora* and *Ipomea*, *Sesuvium*. Floodplain vegetation is mainly *Sporobolus africanus* (Seck 2014).

Figure 7. Mangroves defined as “vegetation”. Source: Gbane 2019.

6. Data and methods

6.1. Overview of approach

This study used several GIS procedures within ArcGIS version 10.7.1 to analyze land cover change, and was supported by Google Earth Pro. The methodology was intended to be easily replicated. To be able to work with the data, the delimited study area was drawn into a polygon shapefile created in ArcCatalog named *study_area*. Then, the remote sensing data used, explained in further detail below, was clipped into the *study_area* (table 1).

Each of the clipped resulting Landsat images was used to run a Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI) and a Maximum Likelihood Classification (MLC) (Sandholt et al. 2003, Swetnam et al. 2010, Banerjee et al. 2013, Sinha et al. 2015, Amuti et al. 2014, Dandan Xu et al. 2014). SAVI was carried out to assess the quality and distribution of the vegetation biomass for each year and to assess the evolution from 2003 to 2020. MLC was developed to assess land cover change. The results were analyzed by means of difference raster using Map Algebra in the case of the SAVIs and by means of reclassification for the MLCs. An accuracy assessment, a Kappa matrix, was carried with the help of Google Earth Pro and field observations.

6.2. Data

Data was retrieved from the United States Geological Survey (USGS) GloVis website in the form of Landsat 5 TM, Landsat 7, and Landsat 8 satellite imagery (USGS, 2020). As part of the criteria for selection, photographs had to have less than 5% cloud cover, meaning they had to be taken from between November and March during the cold dry season to avoid cloud coverage (Bouisse et al. 2011, Frederiksen et al. 1992). A total of four images were downloaded in raster, tiff format: (1) 15.01.2003, 0% cloud cover, Landsat 7, (2) 01.12.2006, 0% cloud cover, Landsat 5, (3) 06.02.2014, 0.05% cloud cover, Landsat 8, (4) 07.02.2020, 0.07% cloud cover, Landsat 8

(table 1) (Fig.5). Landsat 7 started failing in May 2003 but the image this study uses dates January 2003 (USGS, 2020).

Table 1. Summary of data sources information.

Data name	Major characteristics	Date of Image acquisition	Cloud cover [%]	Image path/row
Landsat 5	Image with 30 m spatial resolution and seven spectral bands, covering three visible bands (blue, green and red), one near-infrared (NIR) band, and two shortwave-infrared (SWIR) bands, band 6 (thermal infrared) has a spatial resolution of 120 m but is resampled to 30 m.	2006.12.01	0	205 / 49
Landsat 7	Image with 30 m spatial resolution and eight spectral bands, covering three visible bands (blue, green and red), one near-infrared (NIR) band, and two shortwave-infrared (SWIR) bands, band 6 (thermal infrared) has a spatial resolution of 60 m and a panchromatic band of 15 m resolution.	2003.01.15	0	205 / 49
Landsat 8	Image with 30 m spatial resolution and nine spectral bands, covering 1 (ultra-blue), three visible bands (blue, green and red), one near-infrared (NIR) band, and two shortwave-infrared (SWIR) bands, band 6 (thermal infrared) and band 9 (cirrus cloud detection).	2014.02.06	0.05	205 / 49
Landsat 8	Idem	2020.02.07	0.07	205 / 49
Google Earth Pro	Google satellite data, maps, terrain, and 3D data	2003 - 2020	-	

6.3. Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index

The SAVI is born from the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) with a correction ($L = 0.5$) for soil reflectance in (semi-)arid lands. It is the ratio between the reflectance of a near infrared (NIR) band of around $0.86 \mu\text{m}$ and a red band of around $0.66 \mu\text{m}$. It provides an

indication vegetation growth and health to estimate cover vegetation (Amuti et al. 2014, Hall-Beyer 2020). The index is dimensionless and ranges from 1 to -1 with values closer to 1 represent healthy vegetation, values closer to 0 represent sand and negative values represent water (Sinha et al. 2015, Amuti et al. 2014).

$$SAVI = \frac{(NIR-Red)}{(NIR+Red+L)} * (1 + L) \quad [1]$$

In ArcMap, this was accomplished by loading the spectral bands and using Map Algebra for the calculation. Each resulting SAVI was assessed individually, as they resulted in different indices maximum and minimum but were given the same colours.

6.4. Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index difference analysis

As mentioned above, the NDVI and the corrected SAVI provide an indication of vegetation growth, health, and cover (Amuti et al. 2014, Hall-Beyer. 2020). Both indexes depend on leaf density which changes over seasonal cycles (Hall-Beyer. 2020). To assess change over the years, this study compared the SAVIs obtained from different years (e.g. from 2003 to 2006 and from 2014 to 2020). Moreover, the different SAVIs (Fig.8) would give different maximum and minimum values with the same colour spectrum not enabling the comparison between them by visual inspection. Therefore, this procedure was done to supplement the SAVIs obtained.

The image analysis tool was used to get a difference raster for the SAVIs for the periods (1)2003 to 2006, (2) 2006 to 2014, (3) 2014 to 2020 and (4) 2003 to 2020. This raster showed the changes in the index from one dataset to another. This procedure has been considered as the “superior vegetation change detection technique” in a review by Coppin et al. 2002.

Furthermore, an unsupervised classification was carried for the difference raster for the period (4) following the method for better visualization in Cohen WB et al. 1998.

6.5. Land cover classification

A supervised classification, a MLC, was created for each Landsat image. It is a popular method based on probability statistics and Bayes theorem and it has shown to be one of the most efficient programs in classifying land cover/land use with an 83% accuracy (Suhura et al. 2018, Amuti et al. 2014).

First, 30 main representative samples or polygons called training samples were selected for each category. The categories were differentiated in the image based on visual examination of the spectral bands, but also based on field knowledge and by checking Google Earth Pro. Spectral bands were used to better visualize the different land cover classes. The spectral band combinations (table 2) were chosen following Boettinger et al. 2008, and information from the United States Geological Survey website (USGS, 2020). The samples were assessed multiple times by checking the spectral characteristics of each class to avoid overlap between land cover classes. The resulted training samples were merged into a signature file that described those spectral characteristics per class. Finally, the MLC evaluated each pixel and assigned it to the class it most probably belonged based on the signature files (Amuti et al. 2014, Banerjee et al. 2013, Sinha et al. 2015, Verbovsek et al. 2018, Kolios et al. 2017).

Table 2. Spectral band selection for selecting training samples for the Maximum Likelihood classification. The numbers are in order and they represent the number of the spectral band in the Landsat image.

Spectral band selection name	Landsat 8	Landsat 4-5 TM & 7
natural color	432	321
false color (urban)	764	753
vegetation (color infra)	543	432
agriculture	652	-
arid soil (gypsic)	-	157
sand	754	742
land/water	564	147

6.5.1 Land cover classification classes

The land was classified into 5 categories or classes: (1) water, (2) vegetation, (3) low vegetation, (4) arid and (5) sand (table 3). They were chosen following land cover and soils literature, field observations, and Google Earth Pro visualizations. Moreover, decisions were made to merge urban, agriculture and arid together due to issues encountered in the process.

At first, agriculture and urban were meant to be included as separate files. However, the characteristics from the semi-arid habitat, urban settlements and cleared land for agriculture and cattle grazing were too similar and could not be distinguished from each other in a Landsat 30 meters resolution image. Furthermore, the urban settlements are distributed unevenly in the space with houses far from each other. The houses are made from brick or straw and mud with sandy streets which resemble the cleared lands. Agriculture and vegetation are present together with the houses and as the method gives a value to each pixel based on the main land cover, this information (e.g. whether there were small parcels of market gardening) is lost. Therefore, bare lands for agriculture and urban land cover were included in the “arid” category along with tidal flats and bare soils with little to non-vegetation (table 3).

Water bodies comprise the sea, the river, and some small lakes and ponds. Low vegetation is the Sahelian short grass savannah: short grass, trees and shrubs scattered in arenosols and cambisols. Green agriculture lands for market gardening also enter this category. Vegetation comprises mangroves, densely vegetated fixated dunes, green grasslands in the floodplains and some more densely vegetated Sahelian short grass savannah (table 3).

Table 3. Land cover categories / classes for the maximum likelihood classification of the study area.

Category/class name	Description
(1) water	water bodies (lakes, ponds, and sea)
(2) vegetation	Mangroves, floodplain grasslands, and vegetated dunes, evergreen and densely distributed (<i>Laguncularia racemose</i> , <i>Avicennia africana</i> , <i>Rhizophora mangle</i> ; <i>Sporobolus africanus</i> ; <i>Prosopis juliflora</i> and <i>Ipomea</i> , <i>Sesuvium</i>). In some cases: green agriculture parcels
(3) low vegetation	Sahelian short grass savannah in arenosols and cambisols, scattered trees and shrubs, deciduous partly evergreen, low wood density (<i>Calotropis procera</i> and <i>Balanites aegyptiaca</i>)
(4) arid	land with high presence of urban settlements, cleared lands for agriculture and cattle grazing with little to non-vegetation , and tidal flats
(5) sand	non vegetated dunes

6.6. Land cover change analysis

Land cover change was assessed for the periods (1) 2003 to 2006, (2) 2006 to 2014, (3) 2014 to 2020 and (4) 2003 to 2020. Each MLC was reclassified in order that each class had a number (table 4). Then, Map Algebra was used to calculate the changes. By assigning numbers to each MLC and then adding them or subtracting them, a code resulted that made easier the land cover change classification. For example, 2003 water category was given the number 100, 2006 water category was 1. By adding 2003 and 2006 MLC rasters the sum of the pixel of each year was obtained. A pixel that had 100 in 2003, and 1 in 2006, resulted in 101 which meant no change.

The sum of the resulting codes was equal to a land cover change (e.g. code 102 = from water to vegetation and so on) (table 5).

Table 4. Reclassification codes for each category.

Category	Landsat 2003 & 2014	Landsat 2006 & 2020
	Code given	
1 : water	100	1
2 : vegetation	200	2
3 : low vegetation	300	3
4 : arid	400	4
5 : sand	500	5

Table 5. Land cover changes with resulting codes.

code	From	to
101	no change: water	
102	water	vegetation
103	water	low vegetation
104	water	arid
105	water	sand
201	vegetation	water
202	no change: vegetation	
203	vegetation	low vegetation
204	vegetation	arid
205	vegetation	sand
301	low vegetation	water
302	low vegetation	vegetation
303	no change: low vegetation	
304	low vegetation	arid
305	low vegetation	sand
401	arid	water
402	arid	vegetation
403	arid	low vegetation
404	no change: arid	
405	arid	sand
501	sand	water
502	sand	vegetation
503	sand	low vegetation
504	sand	arid
505	no change: sand	

6.7. Accuracy assessment

A confusion matrix was calculated to assess MLC accuracy using the Kappa index of agreement by creating 300 random points in ArcMap within the study area. The points were extracted as KML and loaded in Google Earth Pro. They were categorized following the images for 2020 in Google Earth Pro. The data was again transformed to point shapefile and loaded into ArcMap. Values from the MLC were extracted into the 300-points attribute table. Finally, the data was taken from the attribute table and a matrix was created, with the Kappa index calculated by cross-checking the points. Google Earth Pro images were missing for the date of acquisition of 2003, 2006 and 2014, thus the kappa index could not be calculated for them.

There are three main elements in the confusion matrix: the overall accuracy, the producer's accuracy, and the user's accuracy (table 9). The overall accuracy indicates the proportion of area that was classified correctly. The producer's accuracy represents how well the categories were classified. The user's accuracy indicates the reliability of the map, of the MLC and how well it represents reality (Banerjee et al. 2013).

The kappa index is a calculation to measure interrater reliability that considers chance. It was calculated as given in equation [2].

$$\kappa = \frac{N \sum_{i=1}^r X_{ii} - \sum_{i=1}^r (x_{i+})(x_{+i})}{N^2 - \sum_{i=1}^r (x_{i+})(x_{+i})}$$

[2]

where N is the total number of observations, r is the number of rows in the matrix, X_{ii} is the number of observations in row i and column i , and x_{i+} , x_{+i} are the marginal totals for row i and column i . The kappa index represents the accuracy after chance agreement is excluded. The index ranges from -1 to +1. Values ≤ 0 indicate no agreement and 0.01–0.20 none to slight, 0.21–0.40 fair, 0.41–0.60 moderate, 0.61–0.80 substantial, and 0.81–1.00 almost perfect agreement (Cohen J 1960).

7. Results

7.1. Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index

The SAVI performed for each Landsat image shows vegetation health with a correction for semi-arid landscapes to avoid the reflectance of the soil affecting the index. Water features are shown in a red color, houses, or arid soils in shades of yellow and the health of the vegetation in shades of green, with the darkest green being the healthiest vegetation. The index ranges from -1 (red: water), through 0 (yellow: arid soil) to +1 (green: healthy vegetation). The 2003 index ranges from -0.96 to 0.64 (Fig.8.a); 2006 from -1.01 to 1.07 (Fig.8.b); 2014 from -0.36 to 0.57 (Fig.8.c); and 2020 from -0.56 to 0.67 (Fig.8.d). 2006 index presents some disturbances and a range that exceeds +1 and -1 indicating the need for some correction (Fig.8.b).

Overall, healthiest, and more dense vegetation is in the northeast of the study area, in the lands adjacent to the river but further enough from the excessive intrusion of seawater to grow (Fig.8). There, a small stream of the river forms a rhomboidal land of mangroves. The sandpit and land to the east of the river share similar low indices values. Next to the water bodies inland, there is no vegetation (indices values around 0).

From 2003 maximum index (0.64) to 2006 (1.07) there is an increase in the highest value of vegetation health. From 2006 to 2014 again an increase seems to be happening. However, the index maximum for 2014 is 0.57, 0.50 less than that of 2006. What it looks greener in the map and seems to be of higher SAVI index is a lot less than 1.07 (Fig.8). 2020 SAVI's maximum is 0.69. This shows a pattern of increase after the breach in the first 3 years (2003 to 2006), then a steep decrease in the next 8 years (2006 to 2014) and finally an increase again in the next 7 years (2014 to 2020). From 2003 to 2020, there is just a slight increase in the maximum values (0.64 to

0.69) but what seems to be a general increase in the health vegetation and thus a greening of the area in the land east to the river.

Figure 8 shows the same range of colours for different maximum and minimum indices. Therefore, when discussing SAVIs differences from year to year, attention must be put in the SAVIs range and not the colour of the maps (Fig.8). For example, the maximum for 2003 is 0.64 whereas for 2006 is 1.07, still both 0.64 and 1.07 show the same shade of green. This can lead to misrepresentations. In the next section (7.2 SAVI difference), difference rasters for each period were calculated. These resulting graphs do give the exact change or increase between each SAVI (Fig.9). Limitations of this graph are further discussed in the Discussion section.

7.2. Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index difference

Difference rasters were created from comparing two SAVIs from different periods: (1) 2003 to 2006, (2) 2006 to 2014, (3) 2014 to 2020, and (4) 2003 to 2020 (Fig.9). Some disturbance can be seen in (1) and (2) as the Landsat 5 is used in this difference rasters. From 2003 to 2006 (Fig.9.1) there is an overall increase in the vegetated areas, the highest increase being 70%, the highest decrease, 62%. Furthermore, there is also an overall increase in the SAVIs in the river which can be explained by a higher presence of sediments and nutrients in the water, as seen from the remote sensing images (Fig.5). The decrease in the index for the sea water is explained by the foam from waves as can be seen in the remote sensing images. The ponds and lakes also show a decrease in the index.

From 2006 to 2014 (Fig.9.2) there is a high decrease in the health of the forested area on the east part of the study area and in the sandpit. This being more prominent in the northern part, closest to the breach. The water shows an increase but also no change in some parts. Finally, most of the land show no change or a slight decrease in healthy vegetation (Fig.9.2). The highest increase is of 100%, with a highest decrease of 62%.

The patterns reverse from 2014 to 2020 (Fig.9.3), as there is an overall increase in healthy vegetation and in the lake and ponds. The sandpit that disappeared on the west shows a decrease from soil (0 in the index) to water (-1). The new sandpit created in the east of the river and in the northwest shows the highest increase going from water (-1) to sand (0). The highest increase is 61% and the highest decrease is 69%.

Finally, the difference raster showing the overall change from 2003 to 2020 (Fig.9.4), shows a decrease in the vegetated forested area in the northeastern part, and no change for most of the land area. The sandpit that disappeared results in a large decrease. The new sandpit created shows the highest increase in the index. The west side of the land area presents an irregular

pattern of decrease in vegetation health. Some water lakes and ponds show an increase in SAVI which would mean less water when going from water (-1) to bare soil (0). The highest increase is of 119% that represents the change from water to sand. The highest decrease of 72% represents the loss of the sandpit.

The difference raster is expanded with an unsupervised likelihood classification for the categories “high decrease”, “medium decrease”, “no change”, “medium increase” and “high increase” (Fig.10). It can clearly be seen that the new sandpit created in the top left corner, which disappeared in 2014 and it grew again by 2020, shows a high decrease as it changed from a vegetated sandpit to a sandpit only containing sand.

SAVI difference between 2003 and 2020

(1) Difference Raster

(2) Unsupervised Classification

Figure10.SAVI (1) difference raster and (2) unsupervised classification for the period 2003 to 2020.. Data from US Geological Survey (USGS).

7.3. Land cover classification

The land use of the study area was assessed by creating a maximum likelihood classification of 5 categories: water, vegetation, low vegetation, arid and sand (Fig.11). Before the breach, in 2003, the land cover of the area is mainly classified as “arid” (Fig.11.a). The sandpit has “vegetation” and “low vegetation” mainly in the south. In this case, low vegetation accounts for agriculture. “Vegetation” increases with width of the sandpit and it accounts for densely vegetated dunes. “Sand” is found on the west of the sandpit, facing the sea. Some of the foam from the waves has been classified as “sand”. This needs to be considered for the analysis. The lakes or ponds are mainly classified as “sand” except for three in the south. There are forested vegetated areas in the east, adjacent to the river. From remote sensing images (Fig.5) and Google Earth Pro, it is evident this vegetation surrounds a stream of the river channel.

Three years later in 2006, the MLC shows most of the arid land surrounding the before mentioned forested area following a river channel converted into “low vegetation” (Fig.11.b). There are a variety of ponds or lakes in areas that were either “sand” or “arid” before, perhaps due to a higher rainy season in that year. The sandpit has lost most of its vegetated area and it is converted into “low vegetation”.

The north part of the sandpit has almost completely disappeared by 2014 (Fig.11.c). The remaining southern part is mainly arid and sand, with few “vegetation” spots. The vegetated area above the river has grown since 2003. Most of the “low vegetation” has decreased in size. By 2020, the southern part of the sandpit has reduced significantly, a new one is being born from land and, in the north, a natural reconstruction of the old one is taking place (Fig.11.d). These new bits of a sandpit are mainly sand. Inland, there are slight decreases in “vegetation” but also a slight increase in “low vegetation”.

7.4. Land cover change

From (1) 2003 to 2006 (Fig.12.1) there are mainly changes from arid to low vegetation in the north, east and southeast, and some of it in the north of the sandpit. Thus, arid decreases (table 7). Low vegetation increases from 2.97% to 18.1% (table 6). Vegetation decreases 1.4 km, from 8.23% to 4.32% of the total area (table 6&7).

To the contrary of the previous period (1), from (2) 2006 to 2014 (Fig.12.2), there is an increase in vegetation (+1.84km) going from 4.33 % to 9.47 and a decrease of low vegetation (-0.93 km) that goes from 18.17% to 15.44% (table 6&7). Vegetation increases mainly in the north, also in some small patches in the south and east (Fig.12.2). The north part of the sandpit disappears, thus water land increases (Fig.12.2). The remaining sandpit loses almost all its low vegetation cover, but a small land of vegetation appears in the north of the sandpit (Fig.12.2).

Table 6. Area of land cover categories in 2003, 2006, 2014, and 2020 based on Maximum Likelihood Supervised Classification, expressed in absolute values [km²], and as a percentage of total area [%].

Land cover	2003		2006		2014		2020	
	km ²	% total						
(1) water	11.30	31.70	11.99	33.62	12.45	34.92	12.53	35.15
(2) vegetation	2.94	8.23	1.54	4.33	3.38	9.47	2.68	7.51
(3) low vegetation	1.06	2.97	6.48	18.17	5.55	15.44	6.09	17.08
(4) arid	18.17	50.97	14.63	41.04	13.65	38.28	12.55	35.19
(5) sand	2.19	6.13	1.01	2.84	0.67	1.89	1.81	5.07

From (3) 2014 to 2020 (Fig.12.3), it appears to be not much change in the land whereas the sandpit has greatly changed by extending from the north to the south, retreating in the south and by the birth of a new sandpit from land (Fig.12.3). However, there is a reversal again of the pattern from period (2), showing a pattern more similar to period (1). Vegetation decreases slightly (-0.70 km), from 9.47 to 7.51% and low vegetation increases (+0.54km) from 15.44 to 17.08% (table 6&7).

Finally, the land cover change from (4) 2003 to 2020 (Fig.12.4) shows a slightly bigger increase of 5.03km in comparison to period (1) which had 5.42 km more of low vegetation (table 7). In terms of percentage, low vegetation inland changed from 2.97% to 17.08 (table 6). Vegetation decreased from 8.23% to 7.51% which represents -0.26km (table 7). Again, period (1) just after the breach showed a higher decrease (table 7). Arid had the highest decrease (-5.62 km) from 50.97% to 35.19% (table 6&7). The sandpit eroded thus vegetation and low vegetation disappeared, the new sandpit consists mainly of sand. (Fig.12.4).

An element to also consider is erosion. Before 2003, the sandpit protected the river and the land to the east of the river. From 2003 to 2006 erosion does not happen in this side of the “river” (Fig.12.1). As the sandpit is broken, the river starts getting salinized and impacted by the sea. From 2006 to 2014 an erosion of that land starts happening when the breach is long enough that reaches the study site. Arid becomes sand or directly water (Fig.12.2). This pattern seems to continue for the period between 2014 to 2020 (Fig.12.3).

Table 7. Land cover change in km² per type of land cover from (1) 2003 to 2006, (2) 2006 to 2014, (3) 2014 to 2020, and (4) 2003 to 2020 based on Maximum Likelihood Supervised Classification.

Land cover change	(1) 2003 - 2006	(2) 2006 - 2014	(4) 2014 - 2020	(4) 2003 - 2020
(1) water	+ 0.69	+ 0.46	+ 0.08	+ 1.23
(2) vegetation	-1.40	+1.84	-0.70	-0.26
(3) low vegetation	+5.42	-0.93	+0.54	+5.03
(4) arid	-3.54	-0.98	-1.10	-5.62
(5) sand	-1.18	-0.34	+1.14	-0.38

7.5. Accuracy assessment

Table 8. Confusion matrix for MLC of the study area for 2020.

Classified Data	Reference data					Row total	User's accuracy [%]
	water	vegetation	low vegetation	arid	sand		
water	109	0	0	0	3	112	97
vegetation	2	25	1	0	0	28	89
low vegetation	0	2	39	2	0	43	91
arid	9	1	10	69	9	98	70
sand	0	0	0	0	19	19	100
Column Total	120	28	50	71	31	300	
Producer's accuracy [%]	91	89	78	97	61		
Overall accuracy - 87%						Kappa = 0.80	

The MLC procedure evaluation through a confusion matrix and calculation of a kappa index of agreement showed an overall accuracy of 87% and a kappa value of 0.80 (table 8). This indicates a substantial strength of agreement between the classified data (by means of MLC) and the reference data of Google Earth Pro (Cohen J 1960). The highest producer's accuracy, which is the accuracy of Google Earth Pro observations being correctly classified by MLC, was found in the arid category (97%) (table 8). Sand showed the lowest accuracy (61%), low vegetation accuracy was the second lowest but still high (78%). The highest user's accuracy, that of the MLC, was found in the sand category (100%) while arid presents the lowest accuracy (70%) (table 8). The MLC almost equally misrepresented water, low vegetation, and sand to arid.

8. Discussion

Salt intrusion and coastal erosion poses a threat to communities. Specially the salinization of land and aquifers is a high risk for a region that is already facing water stress due to climate variability and population dynamics (Giraldo-Osorio & García-Galiano 2012). These impacts also change the way land is used. This report studies those changes to see how big these impacts are and to spatially position the challenges for the future of this region and any region facing similar issues in the world.

The key aspects of the results of this study is an increase of 5.03 km from 2003 to 2020 of the low vegetation class (Fig.12.4) but a decrease of 0.26 km in the more densely vegetated class (table 7). In 2003, 51% of total land was arid land (table 6). In 2020, only 35%. As seen in Google Earth Pro, this land was used for grazing and agriculture in 2003. In 2020, the land cover has changed to low vegetation (Fig.12.4) (Sy BA 2015, Lange et al. 2012, Mietton et al. 2007) . This could represent the salt intrusion in the land and their decrease in land quality also supported by the SAVIs (Fig.9). Therefore, arid land changed to low vegetation due to the abandonment of the lands for agriculture and cattle grazing because of salinization of the wells and lands. There was a subsequent natural revegetation of the area. The land might not have been suitable for agriculture and the wells might have had high concentrations of salt for cattle but it is still suitable for vegetation adapted to these conditions (Sy BA 2015, Seck 2014).

The dense vegetation decreases slightly (-0.26 km) (Fig.12). The SAVIs also show a decrease in its health which could also mean degradation due to salinization (Fig.10). In the mangrove in the north, the decrease in health happens mainly next to the stream (Fig. 10) This can also be an indication of excessive salt concentrations in the river water. Furthermore, land cover changes from vegetation to arid and a decrease in SAVIs in the sandpit and in the east of

the river show the dunes retreating as also reported by Derooin et al. 2012. Some species like *Balanites aegyptiaca* might be incentivized while others perish (Seck 2014). This destabilizes the fixated dunes as it was the case for the sandpit and increases coastal erosion to the point that the sandpit where touristic houses were, disappeared (Seck 2014, Sy BA 2015).

Water changes specially in the water bodies inland, mainly to seasonal changes and droughts or floods. These areas might be of great importance to study more in depth. They might give a good indication of the degree of seawater intrusion. These bodies of water are increasingly being used as places where to collect and dry salt to sell (Photograph 5 in the appendix).

In terms of accuracy, the high results might be due to this report using broad categories that encompass various others. If this report had had classified the area into more categories, then the accuracy would have decreased. Spatial resolution and pixel resolution also play a role. The river in the forested area is so small that the MLC could not classify the river channel as water but as vegetation which was the main category for the pixel. Also, some of the random points created fell in the border between two categories. However, this report proves useful in representing the main land covers and the changes over time.

8.1. Limitations

Limitations play a role in the accuracy and development of this report. Agriculture and urban could not be represented, foam is confused with sand, some of the remote sensing images would need a calibration to better depict reality. However, this report details the changes occurred in diverse periods some kilometers south of the breach which can be helpful in further studies not only at the same study area but worldwide when studying coastal erosion and seawater intrusion.

The unique characteristic of the market agriculture of the study area is that it is developed in between the houses at small to medium scale. Therefore, a 30-meter resolution Landsat image transformed into pixels on ArcMap is not precise enough to recognize it. Therefore, some of the agriculture is lost. Higher resolution images should be helpful in assessing changes in agriculture and urban settlements. There is a need for land cover change methods and images to be of higher accuracy for more precise results (Aitkenhead et al. 2008). Until then, this study must focus only in land cover changes of vegetation, low vegetation, sand, arid and water.

Moreover, another important limitation is the differences between Landsat 5, 7 and 8 which in a more in-depth study should be addressed by doing the necessary calibrations (Cohen WB et al. 1998, Dandan Xu et al. 2014, March et al. 2012). Adding to these methodological limitations, the MLC could have been more complete by integrating the SAVI in the classification as explored by Amuti et al, 2014. Finally, another component that might damage the quality of the satellite imagery and thus of the MLC and should be considered for future reports is the aerosol content in the atmosphere (Frederiksen et al. 1992).

The final important limitation is that each resulting SAVI uses the same colours despite having different maximum and minimum indices values (Fig.8). Therefore, when assessing the results of this report, greater attention should be put into numbers to compare SAVIs more precisely from the different years than into the visuals. Each SAVI and SAVI difference were assessed individually.

9. Conclusion

Gandiol is a unique case as each case is unique in its own way. As studied by multiple authors in diverse cases of coastal erosion around the world, multiple stakeholders should be considered not only in such important measures as a breach in a protective sandpit but in the management, conservation of the area and development in a sustainable way (Walter 2018, Kacimov et al. 2009, Goebels et al. 201, Eissa et al. 2016, Khalil et al. 2013, Mensah et al. 2013, Musa et al. 2016). A breach such as the one conducted in October 2003 at La Langue de Barbarie should consider diverse sectors such as the environment, the economy, the livelihoods that depend on it, etc. Furthermore, as explored by Hudson 2017 and Hudson 2018, and extrapolating it to this specific case, the implementation of these measures, as with the construction of dams, should follow a planning phase where hydrologic and environmental baseline conditions are considered for the management of the coastal lands. Because a human-made measure as small as a breach of 4 meters can have disastrous consequences.

Seawater intrusion and coastal erosion puts fisheries, tourism, agriculture, and cattle grazing at risk, damaging livelihoods, fauna, and flora dependent on them. This report has shown how coastal erosion can change dramatically the land cover. It made an area (the sandpit) where unique habitats existed jointly with agriculture and touristic activities and hotels disappear. Most importantly, it completely changed the economic activities of a community by making those activities impossible to be carried out, posing threats to water and food security in the area.

Most countries are not prepared to prevent the impacts of salinization due to overexploitation of groundwater, dam construction and thus streamflow disturbances or sea level rise and “ad hoc maladapted responses” are put in place (Mensah et al 2013, Hudson 2017). In this case, the breach was not due to the factors mentioned above but due to flooding. However,

this ad hoc response in such a dynamic and complex system as La Langue de Barbarie which separates the freshwater of the river from the sea, created unseen responses that are still today, 17 years later, causing struggle in the area. The consequences of this breach are similar to those of sea level rise, overexploitation of groundwater and dam construction and happen internationally (Mensah et al. 2013, Kacimov et al. 2009, Goebels et al. 2017, Eissa et al. 2016, Khalil et al. 2013, Musa et al. 2016). As in Mensah et al. 2013 the breach created property and livelihood loss, economic stagnation, and saltwater intrusion which in turn translated in diverse land cover changes.

Future research, following advice from literature and supported by this project's results, should focus on expanding the understanding of seawater intrusion impacts in soil and freshwater. This then would allow the implementation of projects and policies for the protection of the environment and the livelihoods of the people, especially in developing communities (Walter 2018, Kacimov et al. 2009, Goebels et al. 201, Eissa et al. 2016, Khalil et al. 2013, Mensah et al. 2013, Musa et al. 2016). Furthermore, literature recommends developing regional vulnerability evaluation models (VEMs) adding land cover maps to better understand how indicators of vulnerability play a role in it spatially (Salvati et al. 2009, Stitger et al. 2006).

In conclusion, this study shows complex dynamics of coastal erosion and seawater intrusion in land cover change. It is an essential work that could represent the basis for studying land cover changes in semi-arid environments. Furthermore, with added information such as salt concentration, biodiversity in fauna and flora, groundwater, or soil characteristics, it could help understand coastal erosion and seawater change and help preventing or mitigating these impacts. It can also be used in other communities at risk of seawater intrusion or erosion as a starting point to understand vulnerability and land cover dynamics.

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APPENDICES

A. Field images

All images were taken by the author at the study site in the days between 16th January 2020 and 19th January 2020.

Photograph 1. Attempts to protect a holiday house with rocks and metal protections.

Photograph 2. Back door that used to give access to the beach at a holiday house. Rocks are put in the place to try to stop erosion and protect the property.

Photograph 3. Beach erosion at the study area.

Photograph 4. Last remains of market gardening agriculture at the study area.

Photograph 5. Salinized flooding area that floods in the wet season (summer).

Photograph 6. Close up of salinized area.

Photograph 7. Preparation of salt to sell from the flooding area (photograph 6).

Photograph 8. Dead vegetation and salt.

Photograph 9. Beach erosion and vegetation loss.

Photograph 10. Beach erosion.

Photograph 11. Beach erosion II.

Photograph 12. Touristic houses destroyed by the sea.

Photograph 13. Picture taken from the light house at Pilote Barre. Northern views of the new sandpit and trees planted to try to stop coastal erosion, and the village. In the west there are abandoned pirogues. On the east, there is an abandoned field for market gardening. Along the coastline there are destroyed houses for tourism

Photograph 14. Picture taken from the light house at Pilote Barre. Southern views of the southern part of the new sandpit. Again, there are abandoned pirogues and small parcels for market gardening.

Photograph 15. The sandpit where hotels used to stand. On the right we can see some dead planted trees.